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STUDY ON PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES, SENSORY EVALUATION OF PINEAPPLE POMACE INCORPORATED MULTIGRAIN BISCUIT

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Abstract

The bakery industry prepared cookies by using refined wheat flour in India and worldwide, that long-term result leads to health problems viz., constipation, obesity, imbalance, etc. Cookies possess some attractive features including, a large consumption base and relatively long shelf life. Pineapple pomace even after extraction of juice contains the most valuable compounds in producing functional food due to the presence of natural flavoring ingredients, fibers, several bioactive compounds and mineral etc. therefore the aim of the study was to investigate the sensory quality and nutritional composition of multigrain biscuit incorporated with pineapple pomace powder at different proportions (5%, 10%, 15%, and 20%). Among the treatments biscuits prepared by using 15 percent, pineapple pomace powder had the highest sensory scores having the 8.27 by panel members and 8.39 by ultimate consumers of overall acceptability. The proximate content of moisture, carbohydrates, protein, fat, energy, fiber and minerals like calcium and iron were significantly ($p < 0.05\%$) analyzed. Proximate analysis shows that the biscuits incorporated with pineapple pomace powder have higher nutritional values Carbohydrate 61.06 ± 0.69 Protein 14.16 ± 0.74 Fat 18.33 ± 1.01 Fiber 8.16 ± 0.42 Calcium 39.69 ± 1.41 Iron 2.08 ± 0.83 .

Keywords: Biscuit, Sensory Analysis, Pineapple, Chemical Constituents, Proximate.

1. Introduction

Cookies are one of the most delicious foods most people like. Cookies represent the largest category of snack items in baked goods (Pratima and Yadav, 2000). They are stable foods and have advantages such as ready-to-eat and variety in form, wide consumption, and long shelf life (Siddiqui and Nasreen, 2014). Currently, biscuits are made from complex wheat flour or fortified with other excellent nutrient sources (Wani et al., 2015). By changing the basic recipe and incorporating new ingredients such as fiber, fat substitutes, and grains other than wheat, a new biscuit formulation with improved functionality and nutritional value was born (Handa et al., 2012; Yadav et al., 2012). Fruits are produced in large quantities and consumed locally, but are rarely processed for added value. Fruits exhibit a relatively high metabolic activity compared to other plant-based foods such as seeds and tubers (Offia-Olua and Ekwunife, 2015). Hence, the commercial use of varieties of fruit requires diversity. There are many ways to utilize and process fruit, including juices, jams, concentrates, jellies, and processing into dried products. The introduction of fruit-based complex wheat flour is new. Fruits and vegetables have recently received a great deal of attention as a source of biologically active substances due to their antioxidant, anticarcinogenic and antimutagenic properties (Tortoe et al., 2014). Pineapple (*Ananas comosus*) is grown in the tropical and subtropical regions of the world and is known for its attractive sensory and nutritional properties. It is also an excellent source of carotene and ascorbic acid and is rich in vitamin B1. It also, contains carbohydrates, protein, fiber, calcium, and iron (Ade et al., 2015). Therefore, an alternative solution is to develop pineapple powder from pineapple pulp as a value-added ingredient for the bakery and confectionery industry (Deliza et al., 2005).

2. Methodology

2.1 Standardization of biscuits: Cookies are one of the best known quick snack products. They are characterized by a formula high in sugar and shortenings and low in water. The main ingredients of cookies are wheat flour, fat and sugar. The chemical composition of cookies is of significant importance as they contain 22-30 percent of fat, 4-8 percent protein content and 60-70 percent carbohydrate. (Farheena Iftikhar et al., 2015). Adding pineapple pomace powder may additionally improve nutritional quality of the products. Different proportions of wheat flour, finger millet flour, and oats flour were mixed with other ingredients to preparation of biscuits.

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Table 1 Standardization of biscuits

S. No.	Ingredients	Levels of incorporation				
		Control(T0)	T1	T2	T3	T4
1	Wheat flour(g)	100	45	40	35	30
2	Finger millet(g)		25	25	25	25
3	Oats flour(g)		25.	25	25	25
4	Milk (ml)	50ml	50ml	50ml	50ml	50ml
5	Pineapple pomace powder(g)		5	10	15	20
6	Butter	40g	40g	40g	40g	40g

2.2 Selection of Judges

A panel of twenty judges (10 judges who have knowledge about flavour, colour, texture, taste etc. and 10 were ultimate consumers) were selected for the evaluation of the acceptability of developed products prepared during investigation.

2.3 Moisture: Moisture content was estimated using the method of NIN (2003).

2.4 Protein: Protein content was estimated by determining the nitrogen present in the sample using microkjeldhal method (NIN, 2003).

2.5 Fat: The fat content of all the samples were estimated by using the method of (NIN,2003).

2.6 Fibre: The fibre content was estimated by acid alkali digestion method as suggested by NIN (2003).

2.7 Ash: Ash content of the samples was determined by the method suggested by (NIN, 2003).

2.8 Carbohydrate: The Carbohydrate content of sample was calculated by difference method (NIN 2003).

Carbohydrate content (g/100g) = 100 – (moisture + protein + crude fibre + fat + ash)

2.9 Energy: The energy value of sample was calculated by using physiological fuel value per gram of protein, fat and carbohydrate NIN (2003).

Energy content (kcal/100g) = (% protein × 4) + (% carbohydrate × 4) + (% fat × 9)

2.10 Determination of calcium: It was estimated by titrimetric method (Cheng and Bray, 1951).

2.11 Iron: Iron was analysed using atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

2.12 Statistical analysis: Data were analyzed using three-way ANOVA and the SPSS software version 20.0. The t-test was used to compare differences in proximate composition between plain cake and multigrain cake.

3. Result discussion

3.1 Pineapple pomace incorporated biscuit

Results of the sensory evaluation of the biscuit prepared with 0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 per cent incorporation of pineapple pomace in multigrain flour namely whole wheat flour, pearl millet, oats flour along with control is presented (Table 2). Scores were observed for all the sensory characteristics with an overall acceptability of 8.10 to 7.33 (by panel) and 8.37 to 8.07 (by consumer) suggesting that the 5 percent (8.45) incorporated biscuit was “Liked very much” by the panel members. Among the treatments, T3 i.e.15% level of incorporation, biscuits scored highest for all the sensory characteristics with overall acceptability scores of 8.27 (by panel) and 8.39 (by consumer) when compared to other counterparts. Scores of 8.45, 8.07, 8.52, 8.34, 8.47, and 8.27 were observed appearance, color, flavour, texture, taste and overall acceptability by the panel member and 8.33, 8.43, 8.03, 8.37, 8.43, 8.39 were observed appearance, color, flavour, texture, taste and overall acceptability respectively by the consumer. The sensory score of range like very much” has been scored by biscuit with 15 per cent of incorporation of pineapple pomace powder (T3). For all the other sensory attributes, a decrease was noted. In the case of PPP added biscuit on overall basis, control T3 was liked very much followed by T2, T1, and T4 besides T0, revealing that the addition of PPP in biscuit resulted in an increase in sensory score below 15 per cent incorporation level, decreased with 20 per cent addition of PPP, Therefore, 15 per cent incorporation of PPP (T3) was selected for biscuit making for further study.

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Table 2 Pineapple pomace incorporated biscuit

Attribute	Appearance		Colour		Flavour		Texture		Taste		Overall	
	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2
Treatments												
Control	8.07	8.17	8.40	8.30	8.47	8.23	8.43	8.10	8.07	8.53	8.10	8.37
5 %	8.23	8.23	8.20	8.20	8.07	8.37	8.17	8.40	8.10	8.53	8.10	8.47
10 %	8.13	8.50	8.03	8.20	8.20	8.27	8.03	8.60	8.30	8.50	8.13	8.17
15%	8.45	8.33	8.07	8.43	8.52	8.03	8.34	8.37	8.47	8.43	8.27	8.39
20%	7.27	8.2	7.17	8.03	7.57	8.00	7.93	8.07	7.17	8.03	7.33	8.07
	Treat	Group										
Result	NS	S	NS									
S. Ed. (±)	0.256	0.162	0.275	0.174	0.264	0.167	0.235	0.149	0.237	0.150	0.193	0.122
C.D. at 5%	0.537	0.3398	0.578	0.3654	0.554	0.3504	0.493	0.3120	0.497	0.3143	0.406	0.2568

Sensory characteristics at C.D. at 5%, 1-Panel, 2-Consumer,

3.2 Proximate composition of Biscuit multigrain

The nutrient composition of control biscuit was found to have 8.88 percent moisture, 13.82 percent Protein, 16.15 percent Fat, 72.04 percent carbohydrate, and 0.82 percent fiber, 0.72 percent ash, 287.71 kcal energy. Mineral content calcium was found to be 27.74 percent and Iron content was found to be 1.48 percent. Whereas PPP incorporated biscuit was found to be containing 2.09 percent moisture (Table 2). 14.16 percent Protein. 18.33 percent Fat content, 61.06 percent carbohydrate, and 8.16 percent fiber, 3.78 percent ash, 450.85kcal energy. Mineral content calcium content was found was to be 39.69 percent and Iron content was found was to be 2.08 percent. Significant difference ($p \leq 0.05$) was noted for Moisture, Fiber, Protein, Ash, and Calcium, content parameters when compared with the control. Rest of the parameters like fat, carbohydrate, energy and iron content were found to show no significant difference at 5% level of significance.

Table 2 Proximate composition of Biscuit multigrain

Nutrient Constituents (Per 100g)	Biscuit Control Mean±SD	PPP incorporated Multigrain Biscuit Mean±SD	P CD 5%
Moisture	8.88±0.20	2.09±0.56	0.0035
Fiber	0.82±0.04	8.16±0.42	0.0041
Ash	0.72±0.17	3.78±0.66	0.0021
Protein	13.82±0.51	14.16±0.74	0.0431
Fat	16.15±2.39	18.33±1.01	0.0124
Carbohydrate	72.04±0.62	61.06±0.69	0.0003
Energy	287.71±1.39	450.85±35.23	0.0049
Minerals			
Calcium	27.74±1.39	39.69±1.41	0.0049
Iron	1.48±0.28	2.08±0.83	0.1700

PPP (Pineapple Pomace Powder) incorporated biscuit are expressed on 100 gm.

Conclusion

Biscuits are most preferable snacks, due to its energy contents, long shelf life and taste. In this study pineapple pomace powder, wheat flour, finger millet flour, oats flour used for the production of biscuits. Sensory analysis shows that 15 percent incorporation had highest overall acceptability by the panel member and ultimate consumer. Proximate content in biscuits prepared by the incorporation of PPP and multigrain flour were higher than the biscuit prepared by all wheat flour.

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